

24 **Abstract**

25 *Yersinia enterocolitica*, a mammalian enteropathogen that causes gastrointestinal
26 infections, produces two main *N*-acylhomoserine lactones (AHLs) involved in
27 *Quorum Sensing* (*QS*)-mediated infection processes such as virulence, biofilm
28 maturation and motility. Several genes of the LuxI/LuxR family and of the flagellar
29 hierarchical cascade are implicated in the regulation of *QS*. Ellagitannin (ET)-rich
30 fruits have been shown to exhibit anti-*QS* activity but putative *in vivo* effects against
31 intestinal pathogens may be associated to the actual compounds found in the gut.
32 Urolithin-A (Uro-A) and urolithin-B (Uro-B) are ET derived metabolites formed by
33 the gut microbiota. In this work we show that urolithins, at concentrations achievable
34 in the intestine through the diet, are able to inhibit *QS*-associated biofilm maturation
35 and swimming motility as well as to reduce the levels of C6-HSL and 3-oxo-C6-HSL
36 in *Y. enterocolitica* without limiting its growth capacity. Our results also indicate that
37 Uro-A and Uro-B may act through different mechanisms and that the observed
38 inhibitory effects are not associated to a decrease in the transcription levels of some of
39 the genes related to the synthesis of AHLs (*yenI* and *yenR*) or to the motility (*flhDC*,
40 *fliA*, *fleB*). These results suggest that urolithins may exert antipathogenic effects in the
41 gut against *Y. enterocolitica* and highlight the need to investigate the antipathogenic *in*
42 *vivo* properties of plant derived metabolites.

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48 **INTRODUCTION**

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50 Bacteria communicate by producing and responding to small diffusible molecules
51 named autoinducers in a cell-density-dependent manner. This process has been called
52 quorum sensing (*QS*). Autoinducers accumulate during growth and, upon reaching a
53 critical concentration, bind to and activate receptors which, in turn, can regulate gene
54 expression and control diverse physiological processes such as virulence, biofilm
55 formation, swarming and motility (1). *N*-acylhomoserine lactones (AHLs) have been
56 intensely studied and are the main autoinducers produced by Gram-negative pathogenic
57 bacteria such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and several members of the genus *Yersinia*
58 (14).

59 *Y. enterocolitica* is an enteropathogen to humans and rodents that causes
60 gastrointestinal infections including mesenterial lymphadenitis after the consumption of
61 contaminated foods (15). *Y. enterocolitica* synthesise two main AHLs identified as *N*-
62 hexanoyl-L-homoserine lactone (C6-HSL) and *N*-(3-oxo-hexanoyl)-L-homoserine
63 lactone (3-oxo-C6-HSL) although three other longer chain AHLs have also been
64 identified (28, 3, 4). At the molecular level, AHLs-mediated *QS* requires a synthase
65 together with a signal transduction system for producing and responding to the signal
66 molecules respectively. The latter usually involves a response regulator and/or sensor
67 protein (4). In *Y. enterocolitica*, a gene encoding an AHL synthase with high homology
68 to the LuxI family of proteins (*yenI*) and a second gene named *yenR* with significant
69 analogy to the LuxR family of quorum-sensing transcriptional activators were
70 identified. An insertion mutation of *yenI* abolishes the synthesis of both C6-HSL and 3-
71 oxo-C6-HSL and indicates that its main role is the synthesis of these lactones (28). In

72 response to environmental signals, a hierarchical *QS* cascade controls swimming and
73 motility in *Y. enterocolitica* through the regulation of three major flagellar gene classes.
74 The *flhDC* operon (class I) at the top of hierarchy is required for the expression of class
75 II genes. Class II includes genes encoding structural and assembly proteins as well as
76 the gene *fliA* which encodes the flagellar specific sigma factor σ^{28} . Class III genes are
77 transcribed from *fliA*-dependent promoters and encode tandem flagellin genes such as
78 *fleA, fleB y fleC* (4, 5).

79 The eukaryotic innate immune system is able to respond to pathogens attack. The
80 discovery of the involvement of *QS* in the invasion by pathogens and establishment of
81 chronic infections has increased the number of studies dealing with the interaction
82 between AHLs and eukaryotic cells. It does appear that AHLs with long-chain (11–13C
83 side chain) and with a 3-oxo or 3-OH group can suppress the immune activity (8).
84 However, pathogenic bacteria are able to produce different AHLs and the effects of a
85 combination of these molecules on eukaryotic cells are not yet known. Hence, the
86 inhibition of *QS* signalling constitutes an encouraging and viable approach to fight
87 bacterial virulence (5).

88 Phytochemicals from plant and fruit extracts have been shown to inhibit *QS* related
89 processes in human pathogens (2, 26, 33, 34, 35). Plant foods associated anti-*QS*
90 activity may be of therapeutic interest since regular consumption of these products may
91 exert some modulatory *in vivo* effects on the intestinal microbiota and prevent the
92 invasion of pathogens. Among some of the fruit extracts tested, pomegranate and
93 various berries inhibited the activity and synthesis of AHLs as well as swarming
94 motility indicating that some of the compounds present in the extracts had anti-*QS*
95 activity against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* (22, 33). Pomegranate and berries are rich in

96 polyphenols, particularly in ellagitannins (ETs), such as punicalagin, and ellagic acid
97 (EA) with concentrations reaching up to more than 300 mg/100 g (f.w.) (18). However,
98 ETs are hydrolysed in the gut to EA which is metabolized by the colon microbiota to
99 form the urolithin-A (Uro-A, 3,8-dihydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*] pyran-6-one) and
100 urolithin-B (Uro-B, 3-hydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*] pyran-6-one) (Fig. 1). Urolithins can
101 accumulate in the intestine of humans and other mammals where they may reach
102 concentrations in the μM range (7, 10, 13). Importantly, Uro-A has been shown to
103 modulate the growth of bacteria in the intestine of rats before and after chemically-
104 induced inflammation (19).

105 In the search for natural products that may improve intestinal health by reducing the
106 ability of pathogens to invade the intestine, it is essential to investigate the effects of the
107 actual metabolites that are formed *in vivo*. In this study, we explore the impact of the
108 ellagitannins microbiota derived metabolites, Uro-A and Uro-B, on the intestinal
109 pathogen *Y. enterocolitica* cell-cell signalling. The ability of these metabolites to inhibit
110 *QS* controlled processes, biofilm formation and motility as well as the production of
111 AHLs was investigated. We also analyzed some of the molecular changes associated to
112 the exposure of *Y. enterocolitica* to the urolithins and related to the synthesis of AHLs
113 and motility. In addition, we examined the effects of a combination of the AHLs
114 produced by *Y. enterocolitica* on human activated macrophages.

115

116 MATERIALS AND METHODS

117

118 **Materials.** Urolithin-A (Uro-A, 3,8-dihydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-one; $\geq 95\%$
119 purity, HPLC) and urolithin-B (Uro-B, 3-hydroxy-6H-dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-one; $\geq 98\%$
120 purity, HPLC) were chemically synthesised by Kylolab S.A. (Murcia, Spain). A stock
121 solution of each urolithin was prepared in dimethylsulfoxide and stored at -20°C until
122 further use. Dilutions of the stock solution were added to the cultures to obtain the final
123 experimental concentrations stated for each assay. Controls were always treated with the
124 equivalent amount of dimethylsulfoxide ($< 0.1\%$). Pure commercially available *N*-
125 hexanoyl-DL-homoserine lactone (C6-HSL, $\geq 97\%$, HPLC) and *N*-(3-oxo-hexanoyl)-
126 DL-homoserine lactone (3-oxo-C6-HSL, $\geq 97\%$, HPLC) were obtained from Sigma (St.
127 Louis, MO). Lipopolysaccharide (LPS), 3-(4,5-dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-
128 tetrazolium bromide (MTT), and phorbol-12-myristate-13-acetate (PMA) were all
129 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA).
130

131 **Bacterial strains and culture conditions.** The bacterial strains used in this study,
132 *Yersinia enterocolitica* (CECT 4315) and *Chromobacterium violaceum* (CECT 494),
133 were obtained from the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT, Valencia, Spain).
134 Stocks of the strains were stored at -80°C in Luria-Bertani broth (02-385, LB broth acc.
135 to MILLER, Scharlau Chemie, S.A. Barcelona, Spain) supplemented with 30%
136 glycerol. Unless otherwise stated, working cultures of both strains were routinely
137 grown in LB broth at 30°C under aerobic conditions with shaking for 24 h. The pH
138 of the culture media was 7.1.

139
140 **Screening assay for Quorum Sensing (QS) inhibition.** To evaluate the *QS* inhibitory
140 capacity of the urolithins we first measured the inhibition of the production of the
141 purple pigment violacein using the biosensor strain *C. violaceum* as previously
142 described (29). For treatments, the urolithin solutions were filtered through a sterile
143 Millex-GP 0.22 μm filter (Millipore Corp., USA) and added to the culture medium. The
144 final concentrations of the urolithins were determined by LC-MS/MS analysis of the
145 culture media and were 4, 6 and 8 μM . 10 mL LB broth was inoculated with 10 μL of a
146 working culture of *C. violaceum* and supplemented with each of the selected
147 concentrations of urolithins for 24 h. Then, 1 mL of culture was centrifuged at 19,314
148 $\times\text{g}$ for 10 min (Eppendorf centrifuge, Hamburg, Germany) to precipitate the insoluble
149 violacein. The culture supernatant was discarded and 1 mL of dimethylsulfoxide was
150 added to the pellet. The solution was vortexed vigorously for 30 s to completely
151 solubilise violacein and centrifuged at 19,314 $\times\text{g}$ for 10 min to remove the cells. The
152 violacein was quantified at OD_{585} using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, UV-

153 1603 spectrophotometer, Tokyo, Japan).

154 **Microbial growth assay.** We determined the antimicrobial activity of the urolithins
155 against *Y. enterocolitica* in culture broths (10 mL) inoculated with 10 µL of a working
156 culture of *Y. enterocolitica* incubated in the absence and presence of urolithins (4 µM)
157 for 24 h. Samples (1 mL) of inoculated culture broths were diluted in 1 % sterile
158 buffered peptone water (BPW) (AES Laboratoire, Combourg, France) (1:10 dilution)
159 and appropriate dilutions were then spread onto LB agar (1 %) (Scharlau Chemie, S.A.).
160 Microbial counts were expressed as log₁₀ cfu per mL.

161 **Biofilm formation.** The effects of urolithins on biofilm formation by *Y. enterocolitica*
162 were evaluated using the crystal violet assay (12) with some modifications (29). A
163 number of wells of a sterile round-bottom 96-well polystyrene plate (Nalge Nunc
164 International, Rochester, NY) containing 160 µL of LB broth and 20 µL of urolithin
165 solution to obtain a final concentration of 4 µM were inoculated with 20 µL of a
166 working culture of *Y. enterocolitica* diluted (1:100) in buffered peptone water (Scharlau
167 Chemie, S.A.). Positive control wells contained 160 µL of LB broth, 20 µL of sterile
168 water with an equivalent amount of dimethylsulfoxide (<0.1%) and 20 µL of a working
169 culture, whereas negative control wells contained only sterile medium (160 µL) and
170 distilled water (40 µL). After 24 h of incubation the wells were emptied and washed

171 three times with sterile water. The biofilm layer formed on the wall of the wells was
172 fixed with 200 μ L of acidified methanol (33% acetic acid). The biofilms were
173 quantified after the crystal violet was solubilized with 200 μ L of 95% ethanol by
174 measuring the absorbance at 570 nm using a spectrophotometer (Synoptics, Cambridge,
175 U.K.) as previously described (30).

177

178 **Motility.** The swimming migration distance was determined following a published
179 method (4) with some modifications. LB semi-solid agar (0.3%) plates were point-
180 inoculated with a working culture (1 μ L) of *Y. enterocolitica* and incubated in the
181 absence and presence of urolithins (4 μ M) at 25°C for 24 h. At the end of the incubation
182 period, the swimming migration distance was calculated using a contrast camera
183 imaging system (Synoptics, Cambridge, United Kingdom).

184

185 **Evaluation of the effects of urolithins on the levels of AHLs produced by *Y.***
186 ***enterocolitica* using LC-MS/MS.** The identification and quantification of the
187 production of C6-HSL and 3-oxo-C6-HSL by *Y. enterocolitica* was carried out by LC-
188 MS/MS as previously described (20, 30). To assess a specific inhibitory effect of the
189 urolithins on the levels of each of the AHLs, 50 mL of LB were inoculated with 100 µL
190 of a working culture of *Y. enterocolitica* in the absence and presence of Uro-A or Uro-B
191 (4 µM) and incubated for 48 h. After incubation, bacterial cells were removed by
192 centrifugation at 9,632 ×g at 4°C for 15 min and the supernatants were filtered through a
193 Millex-GP 0.22 µm filter (Millipore Corp.). The cell-free culture supernatants were
194 extracted (×2) with 50 mL of acidified ethyl acetate (0.5% formic acid). The organic
195 phase was evaporated under reduced pressure at 35°C and the residue reconstituted in 2
196 mL of methanol. Methanol was removed in a Speedvac® concentrator (Savant SPD
197 21P, Waltham, MA) and the residue re-dissolved in 400 µL of methanol, filtered
198 through a Millex-HV₁₃ 0.45µm filter (Millipore Corp.) and stored at –20°C prior to
199 analysis by LC-MS/MS.

200 To investigate a putative direct interaction between the urolithins and the AHLs which
201 may cause transformation and (or) degradation of the AHLs and, consequently, a
202 reduction of the AHLs detected in the culture media, we also measured the levels of C6-
203 HSL and 3-oxo-C6-HSL after incubation of a known concentration of these AHLs and
204 the urolithins in the LB broth but in the absence of *Y. enterocolitica*.

205

206 **Bacterial RNA extraction.** Samples from control and urolithin-treated cultures (4
207 µM) were taken at three different time points of the bacterial growth curve: 6, 14 and 24

208 h corresponding to the end of the lag phase, the exponential phase and the stationary
209 phase, respectively. Total RNA was extracted using the MICROBexpress kit (Ambion,
210 Applied Biosystem, Foster City, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions.
211 The purity and concentration of the samples were checked measuring the absorbance at
212 260 and 280 nm using the Nanoquant plateTM in the plate reader (Infinite M200,
213 Tecan, Grodig, Austria). Only RNA samples with an Abs₂₆₀/Abs₂₈₀ ratio between 2 and
214 2.2 were used for gene expression analyses.
215

216 **Gene expression analyses.** Five genes expressed in *Y. enterocolitica* and reported to
217 be involved in the synthesis of AHLs (*yenI*, *yenR*) and its motility (*fliA*, *fleB* and *flhDC*)
218 (3, 4) were selected for the study. Primers and probes were designed (Custom Taqman
219 Assay Design Tool, Applied Biosystems, ABI) based on their coding sequences: *yenI*
220 (YP_001005892), *yenR* (AM286415), *fliA* (AM286415.1), *fleB* (L33468.1) and *flhDC*
221 (AF081587). Relative transcript amounts were measured by one-step quantitative RT-
222 PCR (Taqman system, ABI, Madrid, Spain) run on the ABI 7500 system following
223 manufacturer's conditions, using a total reaction volume of 25 μ L in a MicroAmp
224 Optical 96-well plate covered by optical adhesive covers and using Taqman Universal
225 Master Mix (ABI, Madrid, Spain). The expression levels of each gene were normalized
226 to the levels of the housekeeping gene *16S rRNA* (AM286415) utilizing a standard
227 curve method for relative quantification.
228

229 **Human macrophages culture and treatments.** The human monocytic cell line THP-1
230 was obtained from the European Collection of Cells Cultured (ECACC) (Salisbury,
231 UK). Cells were grown in RPMI 1640 at 37°C following supplier's instructions and
232 differentiated into macrophages by adding phorbol myristate acetate (PMA, 100 ng/mL)
233 to the medium as described (25). Cells were allowed to differentiate for 72 hours, then
234 washed with PBS (×3) and incubated for 24 h in RPMI 1640 supplemented with 0.1%
235 fetal bovine serum (FBS) prior to treatment with the AHLs. Cells were then challenged
236 with LPS (10 µg/mL) and the AHLs as follows: i) 100 µM of C6-HSL, ii) 100 µM of 3-
237 oxo-C6-HSL, and iii) a mixture of C6-HSL and 3-oxo-C6-HSL at 1, 10, 50 and 100 µM
238 final concentrations each. After 24 h of incubation, the culture media were removed and
239 stored at –80°C until analysis.

240

241 **Human macrophages viability.** The MTT assay was used to evaluate the effects of
242 LPS and AHLs on the macrophages viability. Cells (3.5×10^5 cells/well) were placed
243 into 96-well plates (Nunc, Roskilde, Denmark) and treated as described above. At the
244 end of the incubation time the culture media was replaced by 200 µL of fresh medium
245 and 50 µL of MTT solution (5 mg/mL) were added to each well (final volume 250 µL).
246 Plates were incubated for a further 1 h after which the supernatant was removed and the
247 formazan crystals formed in the viable cells were solubilised with 200 µL of
248 dimethylsulfoxide. Absorbance was read at 570 nm using a microplate reader using 690
249 nm as reference absorbance.

250

251 **Cytokines analysis.** The levels of the cytokine TNF-α were measured in the cell

252 culture media using a commercially available ELISA kit (Peprotech, Rocky Hill, NJ,
253 USA). The minimum detection level was 8 pg/mL.

254

255 **Statistical Analysis.** Results of the phenotypic bacterial responses are presented as the
256 mean values \pm SD of three independent experiments with at least two replicates per
257 experiment. Gene expression analyses were carried out in at least four biological
258 replicates and RT-PCR assays consisted of three technical replicates run under identical
259 conditions. Statistical analyses were performed using PASW Statistics 18 for Windows
260 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test showed agreement of
261 the empirical distribution of the data with normality assumption. The Levene's test was
262 used to assess the equality of variances and statistical differences between experimental
263 groups were determined by the unpaired Student's *t* test, using two-tailed and $P < 0.05$ or
264 $P < 0.01$ as the level of significance.

265

266 **RESULTS**

267

268 **Screening assay for Quorum Sensing (*QS*) inhibition by urolithins using a**
269 **biosensor strain.** We first examined the ability of Uro-A and Uro-B to inhibit *QS* by
270 measuring their ability to reduce violacein production by *C. violaceum* (CECT 494).
271 Results presented in Table 1 show that, at the low μM concentrations tested, both

272 urolithins significantly reduced the production of the pigment by approximately 20 to
273 30 % ($P<0.05$) and suggest that the two molecules exhibit similar anti-*QS* capacity. The
274 lowest concentration of urolithins used in this assay (4 μ M) was selected for the rest of
275 experiments.

276

277 **Effect of the urolithins on microbial growth, biofilm formation and motility in**
278 ***Yersinia enterocolitica*.** Microbial counts of *Y. enterocolitica* following incubation with
279 Uro-A or Uro-B showed that the urolithins had a very small antimicrobial effect at the
280 concentration tested (4 μ M). The percentages of growth inhibition were 5.4 ± 1.9 %
281 with Uro-A and 4.1 ± 2.8 % with Uro-B and did not reach significance in comparison to
282 control cells (Fig. 2A). However, both Uro-A and Uro-B reduced significantly ($P<0.05$)
283 the formation of biofilm biomass (45.1 ± 12.1 % with Uro-A and 38.6 ± 11.1 % with
284 Uro-B) (Fig. 2B) as well as the bacterial swimming motility (19.4 ± 12.2 % with Uro-A
285 and 11.3 ± 14.7 % with Uro-B) (Fig. 2C).

286

287 **Effect of the urolithins on the levels of AHLs produced by *Yersinia enterocolitica***
288 **using LC-MS/MS.** We next investigated whether the urolithins exerted any of the
289 observed anti-*QS* effects on *Y. enterocolitica* by specifically reducing the levels of
290 AHLs produced by these bacteria. LC-MS/MS analyses confirmed that exposure of *Y.*
291 *enterocolitica* to low μM concentrations of Uro-A or Uro-B for 24 h reduced the levels
292 of both 3-oxo-C6-HSL and C6-HSL (Fig. 3) and corroborated the *QS* inhibitory effect
293 detected in the screening assay. However, and unlike those initial results, LC-MS/MS
294 shows a difference in the inhibitory activity of the two urolithins. Uro-A had a similar
295 reducing effect on the two AHLs (36.4 ± 4.5 and 34.2 ± 6.7 % respectively) whereas
296 Uro-B was more efficient at reducing the levels of C6-HSL (45.0 ± 13.0 %) than those of
297 3-oxo-C6-HSL (18.5 ± 10.7 %). Incubation of known concentrations of each of the
298 two AHLs in uninoculated broth supplemented or not with the Uro-A or the Uro-B
299 revealed that both urolithins were also able to reduce the levels of the AHLs present in
300 the culture media in the absence of *Y. enterocolitica*. The levels of 3-oxo-C6-HSL were
301 reduced 1.5 ± 0.7 % by incubation with Uro-A and 10.3 ± 4.0 % with Uro-B. The levels
302 of C6-HSL were reduced 11.1 ± 1.3 by Uro-A and 3.7 ± 0.1 % by Uro-B.
303

304 **Effects of urolithins on gene expression.** We first determined the variability in the
305 expression of all the genes selected by comparing the transcripts levels between
306 different control replicates at each time point. Differences (expressed as the ratio
307 between replicates) were in the range of 0.7 to 1.3 for all the genes investigated, and
308 therefore, only values above 1.3 or below 0.7 were considered as indicators of
309 upregulation or downregulation by the treatments. Putative gene expression changes
310 associated to the growth phase, but not to the treatment, were also examined by
311 comparing the transcripts levels between control replicates from the three time points
312 investigated. We found that the expression of *yenR* was moderately induced at 14 h (1.9
313 ± 0.5 ; $P<0.01$) and 24 h (1.6 ± 0.6 ; $P=0.10$) when compared to 6 h whereas the
314 expression of *yenI* was not significantly altered at the time points examined (0.9 ± 0.3
315 and 0.7 ± 0.3 at 14 h and 24 h respectively) (Fig 4). The expression levels of *fleB* and
316 *flhDC* were slightly higher at 14 h than at 6 h (Fig. 5) (2.4 ± 0.5 , $P<0.01$ and 1.4 ± 0.5 ,
317 $P=0.14$ respectively) and then decreased to very low levels at 24 h of growth. The
318 expression of *fliA* decreased at both 14 h and 24 h of growth when compared to 6 h (Fig.
319 5).

320 We next compared the transcript levels of *yenR* and *yenI* between *Y. enterocolitica*
321 cells grown in control medium and cells grown in medium supplemented with Uro-A or
Uro-B (4 μ M) for 6, 14 and 24 h. RT-PCR analyses (Fig. 6) revealed that in cells treated
322 with Uro-A, the levels of expression of *yenR* were slightly increased after 14 h of
323 growth ($P<0.01$) and this increase was still observed after 24 h. The expression of *yenI*
324 was not modified by treatment with Uro-A. In contrast, exposure to Uro-B was
325 associated to a noticeable increase in the expression of both *yenR* and *yenI* at the three

326 time points examined with up to ~3.6-fold increase for *yenR* and ~3.3-fold increase for
327 *yenI* observed after 6 h of treatment. We then sought to determine whether treatment
328 with the urolithins and associated changes in the expression of *yenR* and *yenI* influenced
329 the expression of some key regulatory members of the flagellum cascade involved in
330 cell motility: *flhDC*, *fliA* and *fleB*. RT-PCR analyses (Fig. 7) indicated that the
331 transcripts levels of *flhDC* were slightly (not significant) upregulated in *Y.*
332 *enterocolitica* after 6 and 24 h of treatment with Uro-A whereas Uro-B caused a
333 significant induction in the expression of this gene, more evident at 6 h ($P<0.05$) and 24
334 h ($P<0.05$) of treatment. The expression of *fliA* was not affected by Uro-A but was
335 slightly increased following treatment with Uro-B for 14 and 24 h although the results
336 did not reach significance. The expression of *fleB* was found to be weakly (not
337 significant) decreased after 6 h of treatment with Uro-A followed by a small but
338 significant increase at 14 h ($P<0.05$) and 24 h ($P<0.01$). Treatment of *Y. enterocolitica*
339 with Uro-B was also associated to an increase in the expression of *fleB* after 14 and 24 h
341 of treatment (results not significant).

342

343 **Effects of 3-oxo C6-HSL and C6-HSL on activated human macrophages.** The
344 viability of the macrophages was not affected by treatment with LPS or the AHLs even
345 at the highest concentration tested. In the absence of LPS stimulation, neither the
346 mixture of AHLs nor the individual lactones modified the levels of the cytokine TNF- α

347 secreted by the macrophages (results not shown). However, following exposure of the
348 macrophages to LPS, a dose-dependant decrease in the levels of TNF- α was observed
349 in cell treated with the mixture of AHLs, more manifest and significant ($P<0.01$) at the
350 highest concentration tested (100 μ M) (Fig. 8). Of the two AHLs tested only C6-HSL
351 (100 μ M) produced a slight but significant decrease in the secretion of TNF- α ($P<0.05$).

352

353 **DISCUSSION**

354

355 **Urolithins inhibit *QS* associated processes in *Yersinia enterocolitica*.** To the best of
356 our knowledge, this is the first study to demonstrate that urolithins, ellagitannins-
357 derived metabolites formed by the gut microbiota (7, 10), are able to inhibit *QS*
358 associated processes as well as to reduce the levels of AHLs produced by *Y.*
359 *enterocolitica* without having a critical effect on its growth capacity. Our results show
360 that both Uro-A and Uro-B, at concentrations in the low μ M range, equally reduced the
361 formation of violacein by *Chromobacterium* and the ability of *Y. enterocolitica* to form
362 biofilm and to swim initially suggesting that both molecules inhibited *QS* in a similar
363 manner. Inhibition of bacterial *QS* has been reported to occur through different possible
364 mechanisms: 1) inhibition of the synthesis of AHLs, 2) inhibition of the transport and
365 (or) secretion of AHLs, 3) sequestration and (or) enzymatically or non-enzymatically
366 degradation of AHLs, 4) antagonism of AHLs receptors and 5) inhibition of targets
367 downstream AHLs-receptor binding (21, 33). Many natural extracts containing
368 phytochemicals (fruit, herb and spices extracts) are believed to inhibit *QS* by a
369 combination of these mechanisms, mainly by interfering with the activity of AHLs and
370 altering their synthesis (33). Likewise, it is likely that these urolithins may exert their

372

373 **Urolithins specifically decrease the levels of C6-HSL and 3-oxo-C6-HSL in**
374 ***Yersinia enterocolitica*.** In an attempt to determine some of the putative mechanisms by
375 which Uro-A and Uro-B may exert their anti-*QS* effects we first investigated the ability
376 of these molecules to specifically reduce the amount of AHLs produced and secreted to
377 the culture media by *Y. enterocolitica*. LC-MS/MS analysis of bacterial culture
378 supernatants constitutes a powerful tool that has been successfully used to specifically
379 identify the AHLs produced by species of *Yersinia* (23, 28). More recently LC-MS/MS
380 was also applied to measure the bacterial *QS* inhibitory activity of chestnut honey (30).
381 In the present work, LC-MS/MS confirmed a reduction in the levels of C6-HSL and 3-
382 oxo-C6-HSL produced by *Y. enterocolitica* after exposure to the urolithins and revealed
383 some differences between Uro-A and Uro-B in their ability to inhibit the production of
384 each of the AHLs suggesting that the molecular differences between Uro-A and Uro-B
385 (the presence of an extra hydroxyl group in Uro-A; Fig. 1) has an important effect on
386 the anti-*QS* mechanisms of these molecules. To discard that the reduction in the levels
387 of AHLs detected in the culture media may have been caused by degradation of the
388 AHLs as a consequence of chemical interaction with the urolithins, we also examined
389 the ability of these metabolites to reduce the levels of synthetic AHLs in the culture
390 media in the absence of *Y. enterocolitica*. Our results revealed a small but significant
391 direct chemical reducing effect of the urolithins on the levels of AHLs and corroborated
392 that Uro-A and Uro-B reacted in a different manner with each of the AHLs.
393

394 **Urolithins do not downregulate the expression of *yenI* or *yenR*.** Since the reduction
395 of the levels of AHLs by the urolithins was only partially explained by chemical
396 interactions, we also investigated the putative effects of urolithins on the synthesis of
397 the AHLs by analysing the changes induced in the expression of specific genes involved
398 in the synthesis. It has been postulated that dietary phytochemicals may modulate the
399 ability of bacteria to synthesise AHLs by altering the expression of the LuxI and LuxR
400 family of proteins responsible for the synthesis of AHLs (33). Like this, curcumin, a
401 known phenolic compound from *Curcuma longa*, has been shown to attenuate the
402 virulence of *P. aeruginosa* by altering the expression of many genes and
403 downregulating, among others, the expression of the gene *lasI* which is involved in the
404 synthesis of *N*-(3-oxododecanoyl)-L-homoserinelactone (24). Also, the flavonoid
405 catechin was found to significantly reduce the expression of the AHLs synthase genes
406 *lasI* and *rhII* in *P. aeruginosa* (32). In contrast, our results show that neither Uro-A nor
407 Uro-B downregulated the expression of *yenI* or *yenR* in *Y. enterocolitica* at the time
408 points examined. Instead, there was a slight induction of these genes, more manifest
409 after exposure to Uro-B. These results suggested that if the observed reduction of AHLs
410 had been caused through the down-regulation of *yenI* or *yenR* expression, this might
411 have occurred at much earlier stages of the cell growth. The posterior upregulation of
412 these genes, especially after treatment with Uro-B, might have been induced to
413 counterbalance this effect. The complexity of the *QS* gene expression system in *Y.*
414 *enterocolitica* and in other Gram-negative pathogens is not yet fully understood. Unlike
415 other Gram-negative pathogens in which transcription of the *luxI* gene is subjected to a
416 positive feed-back loop mediated by the binding of specific AHLs to the luxR protein

417 (14), *yenR* has been suggested to function as an apo-protein active in the absence of
418 their cognates AHLs and that activates the expression of a small non-translated RNA
419 (*yenS*) which inhibits the production of *yenI* (31). These authors proposed a model in
420 which at low population densities (with low levels of AHLs), apo-*yenR* accumulates
421 and activates *yenS* which inhibits the transcription of *yenI*. However, at high cell
422 densities (higher levels of AHLs), *yenR* becomes inactivated, reducing the expression of
423 *yenS* and increasing the expression of *yenI*. We analysed changes in the expression of
424 *yenR* and *yenI* at three time points of the growth curve corresponding to the end of the
425 lag phase (with lower cell density), the exponential phase and the stationary phase (with
426 increasing cell densities). In disagreement to the proposed model we found that higher
427 cell populations were associated to an increase in the expression of *yenR* whereas the
428 levels of *yenI* remained constant or slightly decreased (Fig. 4), more in consonance with
429 *yenI* being constitutively expressed and independent of the growth phase (28, 3). Tsai et
430 al., (31) also suspected that *yenR* and *yenS* may regulate other genes and that *yenR*
431 could act as a repressor or activator and thus, we may speculate that Uro-A and Uro-B
432 might act by modulating some of those other genes through alternative gene regulatory
433 pathways.

434 In addition to a plausible modulation of gene expression, we cannot discard that the
435 observed reduction in the levels of AHLs by the urolithins might have been caused by
436 alternative mechanisms such as the inhibition of the transport and secretion of AHLs
437 (21), inhibition of the synthase enzymatic activity or the enzymatic disruption of these
438 signal molecules by lactonases, acylases or oxidoreductases (9).

439

440 **Exposure to urolithins is associated to an induction of motility genes.** Bacterial
441 swarming and swimming motilities have been implicated in the formation of biofilms
442 and pathogenesis (11). Our results show that exposure of *Y. enterocolitica* to Uro-A or
443 Uro-B inhibits both the swimming motility and the capacity of these bacteria to form
444 biofilm. In *Y. enterocolitica*, AHL-dependent *QS* has been indicated to be involved in
445 the control of swarming and swimming motility *via* the flagellar regulatory cascade
446 which includes the master regulator *flhDC*, the activator *fliA* and the member of the
447 flagellin structure *fleB* (3). A *yenI* mutant of a particular *Y. enterocolitica* strain (90/54,
448 serotype O:9) lacking AHL synthase activity, also lacks the flagellin protein FleB and is
449 unable to swim or swarm showing that some *QS* genes can regulate, at least in part,
450 motility. In addition, the *yenI* mutant downregulated the expression of *fleB* but had no
451 effect on the transcription of *flhDC* or *fliA* (4). In *Y. pseudotuberculosis*, a complex
452 interplay between its *QS* systems modulates swimming motility by controlling the
453 expression of *flhDC* and *fliA* (5). We investigated the changes in the expression of
454 *flhDC*, *fliA* and *fleB* at three time points of the growth curve in control and urolithin-
455 treated cells. In agreement with Atkinson et al. (4), we observed that both *fleB* and *fliA*
456 were expressed in control cells at 14 h of growth and then downregulated at 24 h.
457 However, we were also able to detect *flhDC* at 14 h. This difference may be explained
458 by the different sensitivity of the RT-PCR analyses used in each study (Northern blot *vs*
459 TaqMan). Also, and unlike the repression of *fleB* expression observed in the *yenI* non-
460 motile mutant, urolithin-treated non-motile bacteria did not show a downregulation of
461 *fleB* but a slight induction. The transcripts levels of *flhDC* and *fliA* were also induced
462 following treatment with Uro-B. As stated for *yenI* and *yenR*, we cannot discard that a

463 down-regulation of these motility-associated genes might have occurred at early stages
464 of the cell growth and that the observed induction, especially after treatment with Uro-
465 B, may be compensating this effect.
466

467 **The effects of urolithins on *Yersinia enterocolitica* QS may contribute to**
468 **ameliorate the inflammatory response of macrophages.** Previous studies have shown
469 that Uro-A exerts potent anti-inflammatory effects on a rodent model of intestinal
470 inflammation partially associated to the modulation of the gut microbiota (19). Uro-A
471 induced the growth of *Bifidobacterium*, *Lactobacillus* and *Clostridium* while it
472 decreased the counts of total enterobacteria and, in particular, of *E. coli*. The authors
473 proposed that the decrease in the pathogens growth may be a consequence of the
474 parallel induction of some of the good bacteria. However, the mechanisms by which
475 Uro-A may influence the growth of bacteria are not yet known. *Y. enterocolitica* causes
476 gastrointestinal infections invading the intestinal mucosa and penetrating the lymphoid
477 tissue of Peyer's patches coming into contact with phagocytes (monocytes and
478 macrophages) and inducing multiple transcriptional responses against the infection (15).
479 3-Oxo-C6-HSL has been detected in the liver, spleen and Peyer's patches of mice
480 infected with *Y. enterocolitica* demonstrating the production of AHLs by yersiniae
481 during infection (17) but the in vivo role of AHLs during infection is not yet
482 understood. Previous studies have indicated a lack of activity for 3-oxo-C6-HSL in
483 LPS-activated macrophages (27, 16). In agreement with this, we have shown that C6-
484 HSL alone or in combination with 3-oxo-C6-HSL, but not 3-oxo-C6-HSL alone,
485 diminished the levels of the proinflammatory cytokine TNF- α secreted by human LPS-
486 activated macrophages. We have also shown that urolithins are able to reduce the levels
487 of the AHLs produced by *Y. enterocolitica* and thus, it is possible that urolithins, by
488 decreasing the levels of the QS autoinducers, may contribute to the acute inflammatory
489 response and reduce the ability of pathogenic bacteria to survive and to cause QS

490 mediated-infection. It is important to note that the concentrations of urolithins tested
491 and able to inhibit *Y. enterocolitica* *QS* are in the low μM range. It has been reported
492 that the consumption of pomegranate extract in rats led to the detection in the colon of
493 Uro-A (7–34 μM) and Uro-B (2–65 μM) (13) which shows that *QS*-inhibitory
494 concentrations of these metabolites can be achieved in the intestine through the diet and
495 suggest that the consumption of ETs-containing foods may exert some anti-*QS* effects
496 *in vivo* in the intestine.

497 In conclusion, Urolithin-A and -B, ellagitannin metabolites formed by the intestinal
498 microbiota, are able to inhibit *QS*-mediated processes such as biofilm formation and
499 swimming motility in *Y. enterocolitica* without impairing its growth rate. This
500 inhibitory effect may be mediated by a reduction in the levels of C6-HSL and 3-oxo-
501 C6-HSL produced by the bacteria, partially caused by chemical interactions between the
502 urolithins and the AHLs. Although the phenotypic responses induced by the urolithins
503 were similar, there were some differences between the urolithins' efficiency at reducing
504 the levels of each individual AHL. Our results also highlight that the expression of *QS*
505 and motility genes in *Y. enterocolitica* was induced more pronouncedly by Uro-B than
506 Uro-A. Gene regulation underlying cell-to-cell communication systems follows
507 complex and hierarchical mechanisms not fully yet understood. Future research,
508 investigating transcriptome analysis, may be useful to further elucidate the mechanisms
509 used by urolithins to inhibit *QS* in *Y. enterocolitica*.

510

511

512

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669

671 TABLE 1. Percentage of inhibition of the violacein produced by *C. violaceum* 494
672 grown in LB broth supplemented with different concentrations of urolithins for 24 h.
673

Concentrations	Urolithin A	Urolithin B
4 μ M	27.4 \pm 3.0 ^a	22.8 \pm 6.6
6 μ M	28.3 \pm 2.9	28.8 \pm 3.7
8 μ M	32.2 \pm 2.6	32.6 \pm 4.9

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675 ^a: Results are all the mean \pm SD of three independent experiments (n=2 replicates per
676 690 experiment). Values are all significantly different from untreated controls ($P < 0.05$).

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691 **FIGURES LEGEND**

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693 FIG. 1. Urolithin-A and urolithin-B molecular structures.

694

695 FIG. 2. Percentage of inhibition of A) microbial growth, B) biofilm formation and C)
696 motility of *Y. enterocolitica* treated with Uro-A or Uro-B (4 μ M) for 24 h. Values are
697 the mean \pm SD (displayed as error bars) of three independent experiments (at least n=2
698 replicates per experiment). Biofilm and motility values are all significantly different
699 from untreated controls ($P<0.05$).

700

701 FIG. 3. Percentage of inhibition of 3-oxo-C6-HSL and C6-HSL produced by *Y.*
702 *enterocolitica* grown in LB broth supplemented with Uro-A or Uro-B (4 μ M) for 48 h.
703 Striped pattern indicates % of reduction measured in the absence on *Y. enterocolitica*.
704 Values are the mean \pm SD (displayed as error bars) of three independent experiments
705 (n=2 replicates per experiment). Bars labelled with different letters indicate significant
706 differences at $P<0.05$.

707

708 FIG. 4. Expression of *yenR* and *yenI* in *Y. enterocolitica* as a function of growth. The
709 relative change in gene expression in control cells at 14 h and 24 h was determined
710 against control cells at 6 h. Dashed lines mark the minimum (0.7) and maximum (1.3)
711 ratio values estimated to be intrinsic variability. Values are the mean \pm SD (displayed as
712 error bars) of at least four independent experiments (n=3 replicates per experiment).
713 Bars labelled with different letters indicate significant differences against values at 6 h

714

715 ($P < 0.01$).

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716 FIG. 5. Expression of *flhDC*, *fliA* and *fleB* in *Y. enterocolitica* as a function of growth.
717 The relative change in gene expression in control cells at 14 h and 24 h was determined
718 against control cells at 6 h. Dashed lines mark the minimum (0.7) and maximum (1.3)
719 ratio values estimated to be intrinsic variability. Values are the mean \pm SD (displayed as
720 error bars) of at least four independent experiments (n=3 replicates per experiment).
721 Bars labelled with different letters indicate significant differences against values at 6 h
722 ($P<0.01$).

723

724 FIG. 6. Differential expression of *yenI* and *yenR* in *Y. enterocolitica* at 6, 14 and 24 h of
725 growth in the presence of Uro-A or Uro-B (4 μ M). The relative change in expression in
726 treated cells (ratio treated/control, T/C) was calculated against control cells at the same
727 time points. Dashed lines mark the minimum (0.7) and maximum (1.3) ratio values
728 estimated to be intrinsic variability. Values are the mean \pm SD (displayed as error bars)
729 of at least four independent experiments (n=3 replicates per experiment). Bars labelled
730 with different letters indicate significant differences at $P<0.05$ or $P<0.01$.

731

732 FIG. 7. Differential expression of *flhDC*, *fliA* and *fleB* in *Y. enterocolitica* at 6, 14 and
733 24 h of growth in the presence of Uro-A or Uro-B (4 μ M). The relative change in
734 expression in treated cells (ratio treated/control, T/C) was calculated against control cells
735 at the same time points. Dashed lines mark the minimum (0.7) and maximum (1.3) ratio
736 values estimated to be intrinsic variability. Values are the mean \pm SD (displayed as error
737 bars) of at least four independent experiments (n=3 replicates per experiment). Bars
738 labelled with different letters indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$ or $P<0.01$.

739

740 FIG. 8. TNF- α levels released by human macrophages into the culture media following
741 treatment of cells with LPS (10 μ g/mL of LPS) and the mixture of AHLs or each
742 individual compound. Values represent the mean \pm SD (displayed as error bars) of three
743 independent experiments (n=2 replicates per experiment). Bars labelled with different
744 letters indicate significant differences at $P<0.05$.
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751 **FIG.1.**

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FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

FIG. 5.

FIG. 6.

FIG. 7.

FIG. 8.